

Publishable Summary for 17RPT01 DOSEtrace Research capabilities for radiation protection dosimeters

Overview

Traceable measurements are necessary for meeting the legal requirements of the [EU Council Directive 2013/59/EURATOM](#). The project aims to develop procedures for calibrating radiation protection dosimeters in various types of radiation protection beams, with a measurement uncertainty of $\leq 5\%$ ($k=2$). This will be accomplished through further research on operational quantities for external radiation exposure and the development of secondary standards for eye lens dosimetry. In addition, all participating NMIs will prepare individual strategies for radiation protection metrology which will be reviewed within the EURAMET community, in order to ensure a coordinated and optimised approach.

Need

Controlling the level of exposure to ionizing radiation for patients and individuals working in science, medicine or industry has been widely recognized as the most urgent need. Therefore, there is a demand for new and improved calibration services for operational radiation protection quantities, to ensure the services provided fulfil the requirements of regulatory authorities.

The International Commission on Radiation Units and Measurements (ICRU) has defined four operational dose quantities for use in radiation measurements for external exposure that can assess the protection quantities. The operational quantities related to area monitoring are: *ambient dose equivalent* $H^*(10)$ and *directional dose equivalent* $H'(0.07, \Omega)$, and in terms of individual monitoring, the quantities are defined as: *personal dose equivalent* $H_p(10)$ for control of effective dose and *personal dose equivalent* $H_p(0.07)$ for control of skin dose. For the special case of controlling the dose to the lens of the eye the directional dose equivalent, $H'(3, \Omega)$, and personal dose equivalent $H_p(3)$ have been defined. Since protection quantities cannot be measured directly, operational quantities are used for monitoring external exposures instead.

Both theoretical and practical training courses, to extend the capabilities of participating NMIs for calibrating radiation protection equipment at a secondary level have been organized during the project, in order to ensure the stakeholders needs for providing traceable measurements of radiation protection quantities can be met. In addition, the obligations to legal metrology and the dissemination of the standards obtained, should lead to better radiation protection.

Objectives

The overall aim of this project is to improve the capabilities of participating NMIs from emerging countries so operational radiation protection quantities are traceable to the SI. The specific objectives of the project are:

1. To develop traceable measurement capabilities for operational radiation protection quantities, including the full characterisation of a measurement setup conversion procedure from air kerma (K_{air} kinetic energy released per unit mass) to $(H_p(0.07), H_p(3), H_p(10), H'(0.07), H'(3), H^*(10))$ operational quantities with an uncertainty of 5 % ($k=2$) or less. The applicable photon energy range and dose rate range are 5 keV to 7 MeV and 0.05 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ to 100 Sv/h respectively.
2. To validate the developed measurement capabilities for operational radiation protection quantities, to ensure that within an applicable energy range, from 5 keV to 7 MeV and dose rates, 0.05 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ to 100 Sv/h, the accuracy of the dose measurement under well-defined calibration conditions has to be at least 5 % ($k=2$), by organising and undertaking a intercomparison in dosimetry, including activities related to travelling standards, technical protocols, logistical provisions, and the evaluation of intercomparison results.
3. To develop and submit draft CMCs for the traceable calibration of dosimeters, thus proving the international equivalence of their measurement standards and the calibration and certificates that they issue.

4. For each partner, to develop an individual strategy for the long-term operation of the capacity developed, including possible regulatory support, research collaborations, quality control, the quality management system and accreditation. They should also develop a strategy for offering calibration services from the established facilities to their own country and neighbouring countries. The individual strategies should be discussed within the consortium and with other EURAMET NMIs/DIs, to ensure that a coordinated and optimised approach to the development of traceability in this field is developed for Europe as a whole.

Progress beyond the state of the art

Prior to start of the project, there was limited accessibility to calibration services across Europe, and two partners (IMBiH and TAEK) were not able to provide such services. IMBiH has now developed these services for calibrations in terms of radiation protection operational quantities, validated them through bilateral intercomparison with IAEA. The quality management procedures used by other partners were reviewed and recommendations have been given to update and improve these procedures where it seemed necessary. The calibration service needs of stakeholders have been identified and calibration procedures are being revised accordingly, to include a full characterisation of measurement setup for the conversion from air kerma to the operational radiation protection quantities, which will be integrated by all partners.

Services provided by some of the partners have been accredited according to new EN ISO/IEC 17025:2017. To validate the measurement capabilities developed during the project, an inter-comparison exercise has been started. The results of the inter-comparison will compare and validate the measurement capabilities of the laboratories, for radiation protection dosimeter calibrations, which will lead to improved radiation safety of workers and public, in particular the health protection of the staff and patients involved in diagnostic procedures thus improving the quality of life for these patients.

During the project, the procedure for submitting new or revised CMCs (Calibration and Measurement Capabilities) for the traceable calibration of dosimeters, will be documented and implemented by all. The approval process for an institute's CMCs, in the context of the Mutual Recognition Arrangement of the International Committee of Weights and Measures (CIPM MRA), will be based on three criteria: participation in review and approved key and supplementary comparisons; operation of an appropriate and approved quality management system; and an international peer review (regional and inter regional) of claimed calibration and measurement capabilities. Within this framework, partners will be able to establish the degrees of equivalence of their national measurement standards as well as the mutual recognition of their calibration and measurement certificates. The new or revised CMC claims on radiation protection operational quantities will be submitted to BIPM CIPM MRA database, as agreed by the partners. Moreover, the knowledge gained will lead to improved measurement capabilities at the calibration laboratories and this will, in turn, enable improvements to be made in radiation safety and in the health protection of workers exposed to ionizing radiation as well as members of the public.

A strategy for offering calibration services from the established facilities does not exist. Some partners identified national strategies for providing calibration services for radiation protection, so during the project, individual strategies are being developed by each project partner and reviewed by other EURAMET NMIs/DIs as this will ensure a coordinated and optimised approach to the development of traceability in this field. These strategies will support the long-term operation of the CMCs developed in the project.

Results

Objective 1 - To develop traceable measurement capabilities for operational radiation protection quantities

The final outcome will be to set up measurement capabilities and a unified code of practice on the procedures for the measurement and secondary realisation of the operational radiation protection quantities. This will enable harmonisation in the field, so the services provided are comparable across Europe. To ensure a unified code of practice, a theoretical training course as well as the practical training course were successfully organised and held, so that all participating laboratories were familiarised with the common code of practice in accordance with ISO 4037:2019 and other relevant standards.

Additionally, a methodology for the design of an $H_p(3)$ secondary standard ionization chamber is being developed in the project, with a focus on measurements at the radiology and nuclear medicine departments. For the $H_p(3)$ secondary standard; the ionization chamber will be calibrated in one reference beam quality so spectrometric measurements will not be necessary. Since its design will fulfil the ISO 4037-2 requirements

for a secondary standard in respect to the energy dependence of the response (less than 2 %), conversion coefficients from air kerma will not be needed, as the measurement provides directly the $H_p(3)$ dose value. By using this new transfer instrument X-ray units can be calibrated in terms of $H_p(3)$ and these used for the calibration of eye lens dosimeters. For measurements in unknown radiation fields at workplaces in radiology and nuclear medicine departments, this new secondary standard chamber provides the dose value with low uncertainty.

Objective 2 - To validate the developed measurement capabilities for operational radiation protection quantities within an applicable energy range

An extensive intercomparison exercise has been organised and is ongoing, so the partners are able to compare and validate their measurement capabilities for the operational quantities identified. A target uncertainty of 5 %, or less, and harmonised calibration procedures among participating laboratories will increase confidence in the measurements performed in the calibration laboratories. This will solve the problem of limited accessibility to calibration services in some participating countries. The comparison was delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic; however, work is ongoing to complete it before the project ends.

Objective 3 - To develop and submit draft CMCs for the traceable calibration of dosimeters

The laboratories will gain more information on three fundamental elements, which will lead to the approval of an institute's CMCs such as: participation in reviewed and approved scientific comparisons, operation of an appropriate and approved quality management system; international peer-review (regional and inter-regional) of claimed calibration and measurement capabilities. This will lead to the approval of the Institutes' CMCs and they will learn how to submit requests to publish CMCs in the BIPM database.

Currently, several CMCs are in various stages of the publication process. In June 2020 project partner, VINS, published 18 CMC lines in the KCDB - 16 of which are in the field of radiation protection.

Objective 4 - Development of an individual strategy for the long-term operation of the capacity developed

The individual strategies, for the long-term operation of the developed capacities, will lead to the provision of calibration services from the established facilities and this will ensure the sustainability of the activities undertaken. The partners with less developed laboratories will increase their research activities and will establish standards, methods and uncertainty budgets for the calibration of radiation protection dosimeters at an acceptable international level. The general structure of the strategy document was adopted by the project partners and they are developing their individual national strategies.

Impact

4 presentations have been given at European and International conferences, such as the CROLAB international conference on laboratories competencies, held on October 2018, in Croatia. Also, 2 posters on the research capabilities of radiation protection dosimeters have been presented at relevant events (such as the 3rd International Conference on Dosimetry and its Application, held on September 2019, in Portugal). In addition, the partners have presented the project results to 4 key standardization bodies that are involved in the ionizing radiation field: EURAMET TC-IR, EURADOS, ISO TC/85 and IEC SC/45B. The project has successfully organized 3 workshops for various target audiences. Simulations of the secondary standard for eye lens dosimetry were demonstrated during the training course on *Metrology and Calibration in Radiation Protection*, in September 2018. In addition, the project partners have implemented three main approaches of the Monte Carlo simulations in order to design prototypes for a $H_p(3)$ standard ionization chamber. Various stages of the prototyping process are in motion (constructed and being tested or being finished and prepared for testing), once complete these prototypes will be beneficial for calibration laboratories and have a clear impact on industry. As such, the progress on the design of the prototypes was presented at each technical meeting, as well as, on the annual EURAMET Technical Committee meetings for ionizing radiation.

A supplementary training course on the practical aspects of calibrations was held in March-April 2019, which opened new research possibilities will be conducted through Research Mobility Grants (RMGs) in the laboratories of PTB and IST. Also, the project website is being updated regularly with progress overviews and highlights.

Impact on industrial and other user communities

The knowledge transfer amongst the participating calibration laboratories, will create impact by enabling greater confidence in the measurements of radiation protection quantities, through an improved accuracy of national reference standards for operational radiation protection quantities with an uncertainty of 5 % ($k=2$) or

less. Partners will be able to use the calibration techniques validated in the project, as well as, the measurement uncertainty which is a vital parameter in assessing the operation and quality of a measuring instrument, to provide traceable measurements. Therefore, the metrology services provided by the calibration laboratories will be more widely available and the calibration laboratories will have an increased capability (calibration, measurement, training, consultancy, etc.) which will benefit the end-users.

Furthermore, the research on the secondary standard for eye lens dosimetry will provide industry with more information on the design of the standard ionization chamber based on measurements in standard laboratory radiation fields and in workplace radiation fields such as the ones found in radiology departments at hospitals. The uptake of the new measurement capabilities developed by the partners in this project is expected during and shortly after the project. Early uptake will also be important for the accredited laboratories and manufacturers of radiation protection devices as it will enable them to confidently demonstrate the performance of their products which will ensure that they remain internationally competitive. In addition, the project will contribute to improving the quality of the information available on the performance of different types of dosimeters. This information will be valuable for the manufacturers of these devices, in light of the improvements to the dosimeters characteristics thus ensuring their clients requirements are met.

In order to ensure that the calibration capabilities are harmonized and recognized by external bodies and at the same level as in developed European countries, information on the performance of radiation protection devices will be included in a calibration certificate from a laboratory accredited in compliance with EN ISO/IEC 17025 [9] or in a certificate with a CIPM MRA logo representing published CMCs. As a result, the end users of these services will benefit most from the improved performance characteristics in light of increased quality of the life that will be due to better dose assessment in the workplace.

Impact on the metrology and scientific communities

The project will improve collaborations between European NMIs which will decrease the gap between emerging NMIs and more experienced NMIs. To ensure the sustainability of the project's results, most of these countries will develop long term strategies for the operation of the developed capacities and they will draft a report on their long term strategy for radiation protection dosimetry that responds to future challenges, for presentation to the metrology community.

The knowledge transfer between more experienced NMIs and emerging NMIs on developing and validating radiation protection operational quantities will be beneficial for the metrological community on the whole. In particular, it will have an impact on laboratories that have either, not established a traceability chain for radiation protection operational quantities or those that need to improve their traceability chain.

Impact on relevant standards

This project will contribute towards the implementation of EU Council Directive 2013/59/EURATOM, by developing procedures for measuring and assessing human exposure and radioactive contamination of the environment as well as establishing methods for the regular calibration of measuring equipment. The project's outputs will directly influence the following international standards: ISO 29661, ISO 4037, ICRU51 and could help to revise CMCs according to the latest version of ICRU90. Research on the secondary standard for eye lens dosimetry, in both dosimetry laboratories and clinical environments, will provide new input to relevant standards (e.g. ISO 15382), on the correction factors for the discrepancies between laboratories and clinical environments.

Longer-term economic, social and environmental impacts

The results of the project will have an indirect impact on environmental safety as environmental radiation monitoring measurements will be traceable and more reliable, and the road transport and import/export of radioactive materials at border crossings will be safer. The results of the project will also improve safety and the radiation protection of the general population via more reliable and traceable radiation/contamination measurements of the environment (soil, water, air).

Lower measurement uncertainty and unified calibration procedures will improve the performance of radiation protection monitoring equipment. This will result in a better quality of life for the general public and workers.

By improving radiation protection calibration services among the project partners' countries, this project will provide adequate dissemination of radiation protection operational quantities. Moreover, calibration laboratories will be able to introduce new/improved calibration services and in doing so, will meet industry's need for higher accuracy calibration services across Europe. Thus, making calibrations more efficient, economical and readily available.

Project start date and duration:		01 June 2018, 42 months
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Internal Funded Partners:	External Funded Partners:	Unfunded Partners:
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. IMBiH, Bosnia and Herzegovina 2. GUM, Poland 3. IRB, Croatia 4. IST, Portugal 5. PTB, Germany 6. SCK•CEN, Belgium 7. SMU, Slovakia 8. TAEK, Turkey 9. VINS, Serbia 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. EEAE, Greece 11. INM, Republic of Moldova 12. NSC-IM, Ukraine 13. USC, Spain 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 14. IJS, Slovenia
<p>RMG1: INM, Republic of Moldova (Employing organisation); PTB, Germany (Guestworking organisation)</p> <p>RMG2: VINS, Serbia (Employing organisation); PTB, Germany (Guestworking organisation)</p> <p>RMG3: IMBiH, Bosnia and Herzegovina (Employing organisation); IST, Portugal (Guestworking organisation)</p>		